

Table S7: Partition scheme and best-fit nucleotide substitution models used for the different phylogenetic reconstruction methods (IQ-Tree, MrBayes and *BEAST). Codon position is represented by C1, C2 and C3.

Dataset	Program	Partition no.	Best-fit model	Partition Scheme
mtDNA	IQ-Tree	1	GTR+G4+F	12s rRNA
		2	GTR+G4+F	16s rRNA
		3	GTR+G4+F	ND4 CP1
		4	GTR+G4+F	ND4 CP2
		5	GTR+G4+F	ND4 CP3
	MrBayes & *BEAST	1	GTR+I+G	12s rRNA, 16s rRNA
		2	TRN+I	ND4 CP1
		3	K81UF+G	ND4 CP2
		4	HKY+I+G	ND4 CP3
mt + nu DNA	IQ-Tree	1	TIM2+F+G4	12s rRNA
		2	TIM2+F+I	16s rRNA
		3	TN+F+I	ND4 CP1
		4	K3Pu+F+G4	ND4 CP2
		5	HKY+F+I	ND4 CP3
		6	K2P	C-mos CP1
		7	K2P	C-mos CP2
		8	K2P	C-mos CP3
		9	K2P	PRLR CP1
		10	K2P	PRLR CP2
		11	F81+F	PRLR CP3
	MrBayes & *BEAST	1	TIM+I+G	12s rRNA, ND4 CP2
		2	GTR+I	16s rRNA
		3	TRN+I	ND4 CP1
		4	HKY+I	ND4 CP3
		5	HKY	C-mos CP1, C-mos CP3
		6	F81	C-mos CP2
		7	HKY+I	PRLR CP1
		8	K81UF	PRLR CP2, PRLR CP3